

TEACHING PERFORMANCE OF THE BASILAN STATE COLLEGE FACULTY: AN EVALUATION

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Abstract: This study determined the Teaching Performance of the Basilan State College (BaSC) Faculty. The descriptive research method was adopted. The subjects of the study were the permanent, and non-permanent faculty members of the college. This study covered its main campus and the off-site campuses in Basilan Province. A stratified random sampling procedure was employed in the selection of the respondents of the study. The National Budget Circular – 461 (NBC- 461) Standard Performance Rating Form was used in determining the performance of the faculty in terms of: Commitment; Knowledge of Subject Matter; Teaching for Independent Learning; and Management of Learning. The teachers were rated by themselves, their supervisors, peers, and students. The findings of the study were: The overall teaching performance of the BaSC teachers is ‘Outstanding’ as per self-evaluation, and evaluations made by their peers, and supervisors. The teaching performance of the teachers was rated as ‘Very Satisfactory’ by their students.

Keywords: Basilan: Descriptive Research: Evaluation: Faculty: Teaching Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the current pace of change, it is important to give priority to educational policies that were developed by educators, especially those that take a comprehensive approach to changing teaching methods. Any reform in educational policy must be structured around the evaluation of teacher performance (Galvez and Milla, 2018). According to research, the most crucial factor in raising student accomplishment is teacher quality. It has been established that the teacher's impact on students' achievement outweighs that of the class size, the institution, and the socioeconomic level of the students (Sanders & Horn, 1998). What is rarely examined, according to Schacter (2001), is how the teacher performs in the classroom and how that performance affects student achievement. The goal should be to improve the quality of actual instruction and offer a useful knowledge basis to improve teacher quality.

A worldwide, continental, and national research theme focuses on teaching performance evaluation. Its enhancement has been given top priority since the role of the teacher in the classroom has changed and appropriate teaching-learning procedures need to be constructed. Without a doubt, the use of teaching performance evaluation varies by location and current political systems due to its complexity (Rivas, 2015; Vaillant, 2016). In order to achieve levels of excellence, the teaching performance is understood as the observable pedagogical practice that takes place when the teacher demonstrates his competency and relates to the expected learning achievements, i.e., the intentionality of education and the execution of

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tasks assigned. In turn, it depends on various factors relating to the quality and initial training of teachers in order to achieve excellence in education (Benítez, Cabay & Encalada, 2017).

The NBC-461 Common Criteria for Evaluation (CCE) is a set of factors of services and achievements which establish the relative performance of a faculty in the state university or college for the period of evaluation. This refers to a faculty member's deep sense of responsibility to render service for the development of the student's well-being and for the advancement of his/her discipline (NBC-461 Guidelines). The faculty of Basilan State College is consistently subjected to this kind of performance evaluation, through the National Budget Circular (NBC) 461 - mandated evaluation of teachers' performance. An insight on the teaching – related performance of its teachers is therefore needed to appropriately formulate institutional strategies to improve the quality of instruction in the college, consequently, the quality of education.

It is based on the premises presented that there is a need to determine the 'Teaching Performance of the Basilan State College Faculty,' and serving as basis, develop a departmental, and institutional-based strategies to improve the college's instructional function, and effectively attaining the specified educational objectives, as laid out by the institution and the state. As a result, an improved classroom instruction thru effective teaching may result from an instructional development program of the college.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE**STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM**

What is the teaching performance of the Basilan State College Faculty, as rated by themselves, supervisors, peers, and students, in terms of:

- a. Commitment;
- b. Knowledge of Subject Matter;
- c. Teaching for Independent Learning; and
- d. Management of Learning?

THE RESEARCH METHOD

This study used the descriptive research design. According to Travers (1978), the descriptive method is employed to describe the nature of the situation, as it exists at the time of the study and to explore the causes of phenomena. Descriptive research involves collection of data in order to test hypotheses or to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study. Since this study sought to determine the 'Teaching Performance of the Basilan State College Faculty,' the descriptive method was appropriate to use.

THE RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The NBC-461 Standard Performance Rating Form was used in determining the performance of the faculty in terms of: Commitment; Knowledge of Subject Matter; Teaching for Independent Learning; and Management of Learning.

THE VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF THE INSTRUMENT

The proposed instrument is a standardized performance rating instrument for teachers as mandated by the Department of Budget and Management – National Budget Circular – 461 (DBM NBC-461).

STATISTICAL TREATMENT OF DATA

To determine the teaching performance level of the faculty, the weighted mean and ranking were used.

III. THE TEACHING PERFORMANCE OF THE BASILAN STATE COLLEGE FACULTY

Table 1 shows the matrix of the means of the ratings on the teaching performance of the Basilan State College Faculty, in terms of: Commitment; Knowledge of Subject Matter; Teaching for Independent Learning; and Management of Learning.

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Table 1: Matrix of the Means of the Ratings on the Teaching Performance of the Basilan State College Faculty

AREA	RATERS				OVERALL RATING	RANK
	SELF	SUPERVISORS	PEERS	STUDENTS		
A. COMMITMENT	4.603	4.419	4.439	3.879	4.336	2
B. KNOWLEDGE OF SUBJECT MATTER	4.653	4.436	4.429	3.814	4.333	3
C. TEACHING FOR INDEPENDENT LEARNING	4.633	4.474	4.422	3.823	4.338	1
D. MANAGEMENT OF LEARNING	4.663	4.373	4.422	3.832	4.323	4
OVERALL	4.638	4.394	4.428	3.838	4.327	NA

On the evaluation made by the teachers themselves:

The teaching performance of the BaSC Faculty is Outstanding in all teaching performance areas. They are ranked as follows:

1. Management of Learning
2. Knowledge of Subject Matter
3. Teaching for Independent Learning
4. Commitment

Overall, as per self-evaluation, the teaching performance of the BaSC Faculty is ‘Outstanding.’

On the evaluation made by the teachers’ supervisors:

The teaching performance of the BaSC Faculty is Outstanding in all teaching performance areas. They are ranked as follows:

1. Teaching for Independent Learning
2. Knowledge of Subject Matter
3. Commitment
4. Management of Learning

Overall, as per evaluation of their supervisors, the teaching performance of the BaSC Faculty is ‘Outstanding.’

On the evaluation made by the teachers’ peers:

The teaching performance of the BaSC Faculty is Outstanding in all teaching performance areas. They are ranked as follows:

1. Commitment
2. Knowledge of Subject Matter
3. Management of Learning
4. Teaching for Independent Learning

Overall, as per evaluation of their peers, the teaching performance of the BaSC Faculty is ‘Outstanding.’

On the evaluation made by the students:

The teaching performance of the BaSC Faculty is Very Satisfactory in all teaching performance areas. They are ranked as follows:

1. Commitment
2. Management of Learning
3. Teaching for Independent Learning
4. Knowledge of Subject Matter

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Overall, as per evaluation of their students, the teaching performance of the BaSC Faculty is ‘Very Satisfactory.’

On the overall evaluation made by the teachers themselves, supervisors, peers, and students, the teaching performance of the BaSC Faculty is ‘Outstanding’ in all teaching performance areas. They are ranked as follows:

1. Teaching for Independent Learning
2. Commitment
3. Knowledge of Subject Matter
4. Management of Learning

The teaching area where the faculty performs best is in ‘Teaching for Independent Learning,’ which pertains to the faculty member’s ability to organize teaching-learning processes to enable students to maximize their learning potentials.

On the other hand, they perform relatively to a slightly lesser degree, in the ‘Management of Learning,’ which refers to the faculty member’s ability to create and manage a conducive learning environment and at the same time guide, monitor, and evaluate student learning.

Overall, the teaching performance of the BaSC Faculty is ‘Outstanding’.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the hypothesis that the teaching performance of the Basilan State College Faculty is ‘Moderately Satisfactory,’ is rejected, on the basis that their teaching performance was rated as ‘Outstanding’.

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